

Screening for Subclinical Hearing Impairment in Type 1 Diabetic Children: An Early Detection Approach

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Abstract:

Background: Atrophy of spiral ganglion neurons and vestibulocochlear nerve demyelination have been observed in diabetic patients. This demyelination is considered an early pathological change in the peripheral nerves of the extremities, indicating that myelin metabolism disturbances may significantly contribute to diabetic neuropathy. The study aims to identify the early onset of subclinical hearing impairment in children diagnosed with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (DM).

Materials and Methods: A total of 134 pediatric patients aged 6 to 17 years with a confirmed diagnosis of Type 1 DM, having an average disease duration exceeding one year, were included in the study. Another 134 healthy children, matched by age and sex, served as the control group. Each participant underwent a thorough ENT evaluation, and auditory function was assessed using Pure-tone Audiometry (PTA) and Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE). The evaluation of hearing thresholds involved pure tone audiometric tests, measuring bone and air conduction thresholds across the frequency ranges of 250–4000 Hz and 250–8000 Hz, respectively.

Results: Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) was identified in 9.70% of the Type 1 DM patients, while no cases were found in the control group. Additionally, a significant positive correlation was observed between SNHL and the patients' glycemic profiles.

Conclusion: Routine hearing assessments may be a critical component of the standard care for children with Type 1 DM. By incorporating hearing evaluations into routine clinical monitoring, healthcare providers can track auditory function in addition to managing glycemic control and other diabetes-related issues, thus adopting a more integrated approach to the overall well-being and quality of life in pediatric Type 1 DM patients.

Keywords: Hearing loss, Diabetes, Children.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a long-standing disorder caused by either insufficient insulin production in the pancreas or inefficient utilization of the available insulin. It is defined by elevated blood glucose levels and is inherited genetically. In cases where patients exhibit "diabetes in situ" (a condition where standard diagnostic measures fail to identify diabetes), hearing loss is often transient, similar to that seen in hydrops caused by disrupted sodium/potassium balance and diminished endocochlear potentials. As DM advances, microangiopathy and diabetic neuropathy contribute to worsening auditory dysfunction. Insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia have been associated with increased triglyceride synthesis, although some researchers argue that hearing deterioration results from central auditory pathway

impairment rather than cochlear angiopathy progression [1-3].

Atrophy of spiral ganglion neurons and demyelination of the vestibulocochlear nerve have been documented in patients with diabetes. Demyelination is thought to be an early pathological event in the peripheral nerves of the extremities in diabetic patients, suggesting that disturbances in myelin metabolism might play a crucial role in diabetic neuropathy. Additionally, genetic factors have been implicated, with more cases of hearing loss noted among diabetic patients whose mothers also had diabetes, suggesting a mitochondrial DNA-linked inheritance pattern. Glucose metabolism plays a crucial role in the inner ear, and deviations in blood sugar levels, whether elevated or reduced, can influence inner

ear function, leading to auditory, vestibular, or combined symptoms, as observed in diabetic individuals [4, 5].

The inner ear is highly metabolically active but lacks the capacity to store energy. Therefore, even slight fluctuations in blood glucose levels can disrupt inner ear function. The importance of aerobic glucose metabolism in maintaining the endolymphatic potential has been well-documented. Although other substrates such as glutamate, pyruvate, or fumarate can support endolymphatic potential to some extent, glucose remains the most efficient energy source. While glycogen has been detected in the stria vascularis, it is insufficient to sustain potential maintenance in the absence of glucose [6-8]. Therefore, this study was designed to identify early subclinical hearing loss in children with Type 1 DM.

Research into pulmonary function during pregnancy in healthy women is beneficial for improving prenatal care and avoiding unnecessary treatments for normal physiological changes in respiratory function. Thus, the current study was undertaken to assess trimester-specific variations in pulmonary function tests and to compare these changes with age-matched non-pregnant women.

Material and Methods

A cohort of 134 pediatric patients, aged 6 to 17 years, with a confirmed diagnosis of Type 1 DM and a disease duration exceeding one year, was studied alongside 134 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. All participants underwent a comprehensive ENT evaluation, and audiological assessments were performed using Pure-tone

Audiometry (PTA) and Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE).

Detailed medical histories and ENT examinations were conducted for all patients with Insulin-Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM). Hearing thresholds were evaluated using pure tone audiometry, with bone conduction and air conduction thresholds measured at frequencies between 250–4000 Hz and 250–8000 Hz, respectively. A structured data collection form was used to document variables including age, sex, duration of diabetes, insulin dosage, BMI, and the frequency of acute complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) and severe hypoglycemia. The incidence of hearing impairment was recorded.

All collected data were organized using Microsoft Excel and analyzed via SPSS version 22 software. Statistical significance was evaluated using the Chi-square test, Mann-Whitney U test, and Student's t-test, with a P-value of less than 0.05 considered significant.

Results

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the study participants, comparing the study group (n=134) and the control group (n=134). The majority of participants in both groups were in the 11-14 age range, with 44.78% in the study group and 40.30% in the control group. The 6-10 age group constituted 20.90% of the study group and 25.37% of the control group, while those aged 15-17 made up 34.33% in both groups. This distribution indicates a relatively balanced representation across age categories, with a slight predominance of younger participants in the control group.

Table 1: Age distribution of study participants

Age Group (years)	Study Group (n=134)		Control Group (n=134)	
	n	%	n	%
6-10	28	20.90	34	25.37
11-14	60	44.78	54	40.30
15-17	46	34.33	46	34.33
Total	134	100	134	100

Table 2 illustrates significant differences in blood glucose parameters between the study and control groups. The study group exhibited a mean random blood sugar (RBS) level of 174.97 mg/dL, compared to 109.95 mg/dL in the control group, with a statistically significant p-value of <0.05. Additionally, the mean HbA1c percentage was

markedly higher in the study group (8.51%) than in the control group (4.99%), also with a p-value of <0.05. These findings suggest that participants in the study group had significantly elevated blood glucose levels and poorer glycemic control relative to the control group.

Table 2: Blood glucose parameters in study participants

Parameter	Study Group (n=134)	Control Group (n=134)	P Value
RBS (mg/dL)	174.97	109.95	<0.05
HbA1c (%)	8.51	4.99	<0.05

Table 3 summarizes the prevalence of high frequency SNHL among participants. In the study group, 13 individuals (9.7%) presented with high frequency SNHL, while all participants in the control group (n=134) were found to be free of this

condition, resulting in a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). This finding underscores a notable association between the study group and the prevalence of high frequency SNHL.

Table 3: Prevalence of High Frequency SNHL in study participants

High Frequency SNHL	Study Group (n=134)	Control Group (n=134)	P Value
Absent	121	134	<0.05
Present	13	0	
Total	134	134	

Table 4 details the correlation between high frequency SNHL and HbA1c levels. Patients with high frequency SNHL had a mean HbA1c level of 9.35%, significantly higher than the 7.71% observed in patients without SNHL, with a p-value

of <0.05. This correlation suggests that higher HbA1c levels may be associated with the presence of high frequency SNHL, indicating a potential link between glycemic control and auditory health in the study population.

Table 4: Correlation between high frequency SNHL and HbA1c levels

Mean HbA1c (%)	Patients with High Frequency SNHL	Patients without High Frequency SNHL	P Value
	9.35	7.71	<0.05

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a prevalent non-communicable metabolic disorder that can lead to various bodily system dysfunctions. Given its commonality in the general population, the impact of DM on multiple organs becomes increasingly significant. The global prevalence of diabetes is on the rise, with a particularly notable increase in India. Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) typically manifests during puberty, peaking between the ages of 10 and 14 years. The incidence of IDDM is especially pronounced among young children, with a prevalence rate of 1 in 11,500 as reported by the World Health Organization and the International Diabetes Federation for the South-East Asian Region [9-11]. This study aimed to identify the early onset of subclinical hearing loss in children diagnosed with Type 1 DM.

In our study, sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) was observed in 9.70% of the study participants, whereas it was absent in the control group. A significant direct correlation was identified between SNHL and the glycemic profile.

A study by Soha M. Abd El Dayem et al. assessed auditory function in Egyptian children with Type 1 DM through a cross-sectional observational design involving 40 diabetic patients and 40 healthy controls. Evaluations included HbA1c levels, urinary albumin/creatinine ratios, and various auditory assessments such as dizziness questionnaires, pure tone audiometry, speech audiometry, tympanometry, and auto-acoustic cochlear emissions. Statistical analyses were conducted using the Mann-Whitney U-test, χ^2 -test, and Spearman's correlation. Results from pure tone

audiometry indicated that diabetic patients exhibited significantly higher thresholds at high frequencies (8000 Hz, 16,000 Hz, 17,000 Hz, and 18,000 Hz on the right side; 4000 Hz, 8000 Hz, 16,000 Hz, 17,000 Hz, and 18,000 Hz on the left side). Furthermore, lower speech reception thresholds, word repetition scores, and masking levels were noted on the left side among diabetic participants. Transient otoacoustic emissions showed significantly lower signal-to-noise ratios at 4000 Hz on the right side and at multiple frequencies on the left side. A higher prevalence of failed otoacoustic emissions was associated with a disease duration exceeding ten years, leading to the conclusion that Type 1 DM is linked with high-frequency hearing loss, predominantly on the left side, and correlates with longer disease duration [12].

In another investigation conducted by Hou Y et al., the auditory functions of 50 Type 1 diabetic patients were compared to those of 50 healthy individuals. Clinical parameters were measured to explore their relationship with auditory function. The Type 1 diabetic cohort exhibited elevated auditory thresholds in both ears relative to healthy controls, with significant associations identified between elevated thresholds and factors such as HDL-cholesterol levels, diabetes duration, and systemic blood pressure. Additionally, latencies of auditory brainstem responses (waves III and V, along with interwave intervals) were notably increased in the diabetic group compared to controls. Correlations were found between auditory brainstem responses and GHbA1C levels as well as microalbuminuria. Notably, only triglycerides showed a positive correlation with hearing

impairment as defined by distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE). There were no significant differences in transient evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAE) between the two groups; however, TEOAE outcomes were linked to age and GHbA1C levels. This study concluded that Type 1 diabetic individuals experience higher auditory thresholds, delayed auditory conduction times, and cochlear impairment, with factors such as HDL-cholesterol, diabetes duration, systemic blood pressure, microalbuminuria, GHbA1C, triglycerides, and age influencing auditory function in this population [13].

Conclusion

Routine auditory evaluations may play a crucial role in the comprehensive management of children with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (DM), given the potential for subclinical hearing impairments to develop as a complication of the disease. Early identification of hearing loss, particularly sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL), could facilitate timely interventions, thereby mitigating long-term auditory deficits. Including hearing assessments as part of the standard clinical follow-up may enable healthcare providers to monitor auditory function alongside glycemic control and other diabetes-related complications, ultimately contributing to a more holistic approach to managing the overall health and quality of life of pediatric patients with Type 1 DM.

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